

An invitation to join our collective funding pilot

The IOI Funders Summit 2022 programme is designed with the goal to collectively shape a pilot collective fund. As well as all the talks and discussions we hope you enjoy with us, **we invite you to take part in a collective funding pilot with us next week.**

>> Sign up by Wednesday November 2, 8pm GMT to receive funds to allocate: [link redacted]

We are pleased to share that we have a collective fund of 130,000 USD – contributed by IOI, University at Buffalo and the Simons Foundation – to allocate towards key areas of opportunity for investment in open infrastructure for research.

Our objectives

- **Experiment with and learn about the collective funding process:** how to engage more perspectives and be more transparent.
- **Look for a strong signal for a few areas of opportunity** that we can help move forward.

Why you should join us

- Utilize real funds and help the conversation move forward in many areas.
- Help us learn how to better design a collective fund.
- Chance to follow up on opportunities.

How does it work?

We will split the 130,000 USD fund with everyone who is taking part – you will have control over an individual pot of money to allocate towards the areas you wish to prioritize.

We will explain more when we see you – in particular, **please mark Tuesday's session on Funding Models (15:00 GMT)** in your calendars.

- In the first set of **hands-on session** on Tuesday, 17:00 GMT (repeated Wednesday, 8:00 GMT), you can learn how this collective funding process will work from our collaborators at GreaterThan.
- The **core session on Wednesday** introduces how we've chosen these funding areas to prioritize funding. We'll also have an opportunity to further refine and help shape these funding areas.
- In the **deep dives between Wednesday and Thursday**, we'll explore the six areas we proposed for this collective funding round in a lot more depth. In those deep dive sessions, we'll hear about research that has been done in those areas and learn about panelists' and other participants' experience in intervening and investing in those areas. The hope is that these discussions will help us each decide which area we would want to put our own funds into.
- Between Wednesday 20:00 GMT and Friday 10:00 GMT, those who signed up can allocate their funds to these areas on the [Cobudget](#) platform. We also have repeated **hands-on sessions** on Thursday 21:00 GMT and Friday 8:00 GMT, during which you can allocate your funding and reflect on the process.
- Following the results of this collective funding pilot (shared live on Friday), we will be looking for the areas that receive the highest amounts of funds and prioritize moving those conversations forward. Your participation in this pilot will help us learn how to better design future collective funding mechanisms.

How and what are we funding?

- This is real money.
- You must join Cobudget to receive funds to allocate.
- We ask you to act as yourselves, individuals, and not your organizations - but we acknowledge this may not be possible.
- All funds will stay within the platform, funds not allocated by the deadline on Friday (10:00 GMT) will return to the main funding pot.
- Come to Wednesday's Funding Framework session (15:00 GMT) to learn more about the six key areas you can fund, and suggest any additional areas.
- Who funds what will be visible to all other participants on the IOI Cobudget page but not publicly.

Why is there a goal amount of 30,000 USD for each area?

The goal amount is a minimum threshold and is **set at 30,000 USD**, because:

- We **aim for three areas to be funded** (for capacity and focus reasons).
- We have **a pot of 130,000 USD**.
- We think something meaningful could be achieved with at least 30,000 USD.

If an area receives some funding but does not reach the goal, we will invite conversation and see if any other organizations/individuals would like to contribute or take the pot further. We will take note of the size of the signal indicated by the amount of funding received, so we can address what might be needed to gain more support for this topic in future discussions. We reserve the right to synthesize findings and prioritize top areas for investment.

What if I don't want to allocate?

- If you have joined Cobudget but are not planning to allocate funds, please let us know so we can make sure to only split the pot between those who can use it this week.
- We ask you to act as yourselves, individuals, and not your organizations - but we acknowledge this may not be possible.

What will happen afterwards?

- We will be looking for the areas that receive the highest amounts of funds and prioritize moving those conversations forward. Each area has a goal of 30,000 USD – this is not a definitive threshold. The platform helps you see progress towards this initial goal, and the area can receive more funding.
- After Friday, we will synthesize the findings and be in touch (within ~1 month) with updates. Any resourcing to coordinate work on the funded areas will be provided in-kind by IOI, this cost is not deductible from the funds for each area.